

A Platform for the Biomedical Application of Large Language Models

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Main

Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) has advanced considerably in recent years, particularly in the domain of language. However, despite its rapid commodification, its use in biomedical research is still in its infancy^{1,2}. The two main avenues for using Large Language Models (LLMs) are 1) end user-ready platforms, which are usually provided by large corporations, and 2) custom solutions developed by individual researchers with programming knowledge. Both use cases have significant limitations.

1. Commercial platforms do not meet the transparency standards required for reproducible research; none are open source, and only few provide (superficial) scientific descriptions of their algorithms³. They are also subject to privacy concerns (reuse of user data) and to considerable commercial pressures. In addition, they are not fully customisable to accommodate a specific research domain or workflow.
2. Individual solutions, on the other hand, are not accessible to the majority of biomedical researchers. They require many specialised skills in addition to the researcher's domain-specific knowledge, such as programming, data management, machine learning knowledge, technical expertise in deployment and frameworking, and management of software versions in a rapidly changing environment. This, in turn, prevents robust and reproducible results due to the many technical challenges involved. As a result, applications of LLMs in biomedical research are still at the level of individual case studies^{2,4}, in contrast to the imaging domain, which boasts several open-source AI frameworks and approved medical devices¹.

To bridge the gap between complex custom solutions and closed-source commercial platforms, we present BioChatter (<https://biochatter.org>), an open-source Python framework designed to develop custom biomedical research software in line with Open Science principles⁵. BioChatter's modular architecture offers broad applicability across various biomedical research contexts (Figure 1 A). Its flexible composition supports a wide range of applications, from rapid prototyping to fully encapsulated deployment (Figure 1 B).

To eliminate redundancies from the frequent reimplementations of basic workflows, we offer a permissively licenced software package that integrates and maintains basic open-source components ([Supplementary Methods](#)). This not only eases the software development burden but also unifies common LLM-driven workflows in biomedicine, making them available through a single, cohesive Application Programming Interface (API, Figure 1 C). We harmonise the distinct APIs of LLM

deployment tools and proprietary LLM providers, allowing the user to switch between different models and providers without changing their code.

We integrate with existing open-source infrastructure such as BioCypher⁶ and other databases, allowing injection of domain knowledge to perform Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG, [Supplementary Note: Retrieval-Augmented Generation](#)). We also facilitate the integration of live services (including web-based APIs) via the LLMs' ability to parameterise API queries, made robust by custom implementations of each API service in BioChatter. Finally, our customisable platform allows users to align the LLM to their context via system prompts, as well as advanced workflows using agent-based systems ([Supplementary Methods](#)). Simplifying these customisations is a major benefit of BioChatter, often achievable by changing a simple configuration file (for examples see [Supplementary Note: Customisation](#)).

We provide abstract classes for the implementation of multi-agent systems based on reflexion⁷. These systems can be configured to perform simple reflexive tasks, such as fact checking, or more complex tasks, such as iteratively improving Knowledge Graph (KG) queries based on their results ([Supplementary Methods](#)). Prospectively, these agent systems have the potential to scale to significant levels of complexity. However, this will require thorough evaluation and balancing between performance and compute cost⁸.

Figure 1: The modular BioChatter platform architecture. A) BioChatter provides a selection of diverse APIs for various use cases (Python, REST) and two graphical user interfaces (the Python-based “Light” for rapid prototyping and the more fully-featured JavaScript app “Next”). B) BioChatter facilitates the creation of custom deployments on a spectrum of tradeoff between simplicity/economy (left) and security (right). C) BioChatter harmonises the APIs of open-source LLM deployment tools and proprietary LLM providers (brown), knowledge management systems such as KGs and vector databases (purple), public APIs (red) of databases (such as OncoKB⁹), and software (such as BLAST¹⁰). In addition, the LLM can be specifically instructed according to the user’s context via customisable system prompts (green). Each use case is then an individualised combination of these components, combined by either manual or semi-automated agentic workflows, and adapted to the user’s needs, including use case-specific validation for robustness. Acronyms - API: Application Programming Interface; KG: Knowledge Graph, LLM: Large Language Model; REST: Representational State Transfer.

To address the challenges of reproducibility in LLM workflows, we developed a continuous benchmarking system that allows the community to monitor the performance of all included models on specific tasks. Whenever we add a feature, such as KG query generation, we introduce a battery of tests to validate its functionality based on community-driven use cases (Figure 2 A). The benchmarking framework runs these tests across all models and relevant parameters and reports the results to the community via our website ([Supplementary Note: Benchmarking](#)). We rely on open-source software to rapidly incorporate new models as they are released, effectively keeping pace with rapid developments in the field by distributing technical tasks across the community ([Supplementary Methods](#)).

In the case of KG connectivity, we see a large increase of performance across all LLMs due to the native interaction of BioChatter with BioCypher KGs (Figure 2 B). Through the detailed description of KG components in the BioCypher schema configuration, we can effectively guide the LLM in using the KG ([Supplementary Methods](#)). In future work, we plan to extend this approach to extracting information from text and images, and we have begun developing a new framework, BioGather, to support this effort (Figure 2 C). A key advantage of this integrated approach is its ability to guide the model in extracting information from unstructured sources, aligning with the KG's schema for each use case. This promotes data harmonisation and leads to multiple synergies: LLMs make knowledge more accessible and show superior extraction performance owing to their context awareness, while KGs make LLMs more reliable and facilitate the harmonisation of extracted information.

Figure 2: Benchmarking, monitoring, and outlook. A) The workflow of introducing use case-specific tests into the BioChatter benchmarking framework facilitates continuous monitoring. Dedicated benchmarks are run across a combination of models and other parameters. B) Comparison of two benchmark tasks for KG query generation show that BioChatter's prompt engine achieves much higher accuracy than the naive approach (measured as number of correct query components amongst all tested). The BioChatter variant involves a multi-step procedure of constructing the query, while the "LLM only" variant receives the complete schema definition of a BioCypher KG (which BioChatter also uses as a basis for the prompt engine). The general instructions for both variants are the same, otherwise (see [Sup](#)

[plementary Note: Benchmarking](#)). The test includes all models, sizes, and quantisation levels (N = 150), and the performance is measured as the mean accuracy for the two tasks (0.486 ± 0.12 vs. 0.844 ± 0.11 , unpaired t-test $P < 0.001$, t-statistic: 18.65). Center line, median; box limits, upper and lower quartiles; whiskers, 1.5x interquartile range; points, outliers. C) The BioCypher ecosystem will cover the process of knowledge management from extraction through representation to application. We will develop BioGather (denoted by dashed lines as ongoing work) to integrate natively with the BioCypher and BioChatter frameworks to allow flexible extraction of information from diverse resources using a unified API. This will achieve two pairs of bidirectional synergies: KGs to extraction pipelines and KGs to LLMs, respectively.

Demands for regulation, an international forum, and benchmarks of LLMs applied to biomedical research have been made^{11,12}, but practical solutions rooted in the scientific community still remain lacking. In contrast to biomedical image analysis, which boasts numerous open frameworks to facilitate access to AI methods, language-based research tasks are at the stage of exploration, case studies, perspectives, and recommendations for manual application^{1,2,4,13}. A prevailing perspective on the medical application of LLMs is that their development and evaluation will be shaped and driven by regulators and closed-source companies¹³, which will likely exclude actors outside the global north. We argue that, instead, the Open Science community should lead the development and evaluation of these new and rapidly evolving technologies in a fully transparent, open-source manner, to allow for an approach inclusive of all groups of stakeholders and the global community³. We believe this to be essential for approaching the emerging challenges in the field, such as ensuring safety in sensitive applications. Rather than relying solely on benchmarking suites that highlight model abilities, a framework based on Popperian falsification—designed to push the limits of these models—will be paramount⁸.

We prioritise pragmatic execution over attempting to create a one-size-fits-all solution. By offering a flexible, modular platform tailored to developers of custom solutions in the biomedical field, we aim to reduce development and maintenance burdens while enhancing the robustness of resulting applications. BioChatter is not designed to compete with existing infrastructure or consumer products. Instead, it leverages open-source infrastructure to efficiently address the specific demands of biomedical research, distinguishing itself from proprietary consumer-oriented products through its commitment to openness and transparency.

Our ultimate aim is to harmonise APIs not only for LLMs but across the entire scientific knowledge management ecosystem. This includes everything from extraction of information from text and images, through knowledge representation, to the application of this knowledge in decision-making, data analysis, hypothesis generation, and scientific communication. We focus on facilitating research tasks that are manual and repetitive, freeing up more time for creative thinking and complex reasoning⁴. To promote early collaboration, we follow a completely open-source development model. We have initiated projects to tackle challenges in research software support, knowledge management, publishing, and large-scale drug discovery through the BioChatter consortium ([Supplementary Note: The BioChatter Consortium](#)).

In the future, generative AI models will be contrastively trained to synthesise information from multiple relevant modalities, including text, images, and molecular measurements such as genomics and transcriptomics^{2,14}. This approach is expected to enhance their ability to aid in reasoning^{8,15}. While some of our benchmarks already demonstrate the excellent capabilities of current-generation LLMs in extracting multimodal information from text and images ([Supplementary Note: Benchmarking](#)), research and applications in this area are still in their early stages. We are committed to updating BioChatter and its ecosystem to support new developments in the field. We encourage the community to engage with these advancements by requesting features, contributing code, and sharing their research and applications.

Author Contributions

SL conceptualised and developed the platform, coordinated the consortium, and wrote the manuscript. SF implemented BioChatter functionality and developed both frontend and backend components for the BioChatter Next server. NB developed the API calling module with SF and SL. AM implemented the local deployment functionality. The BioChatter consortium members contributed to the development of the platform and provided feedback on the manuscript. CW architected the BioChatter Next server infrastructure. JB provided guidance and supervision as well as hardware resources for local LLM use and contributed to performance benchmarking. JAV developed text extraction benchmarking procedures. NK implemented benchmarking procedures. QM oversaw the development and deployment of the BioChatter Next server environment. TL oversaw the text extraction work and acquired funding. JSR supervised the project, revised the manuscript, and acquired funding. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Conflict of Interest

JSR reports funding from GSK, Pfizer and Sanofi and fees/honoraria from Travers Therapeutics, Stadapharm, Pfizer, Grunenthal, Owkin, and Astex Pharmaceuticals.

Data and Code Availability

All data and code used in this study are available in the repository at <https://github.com/biocypher/biochatter>. In addition, the repository is DOI-indexed at Zenodo / OpenAIRE (<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10777945>).

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Supplementary Materials

Supplementary Methods

BioChatter (version 0.7.5 at the time of writing) is a Python library, supporting Python 3.10-3.12, which we ensure with a continuous integration pipeline on GitHub (<https://github.com/biocypher/biochatter>). We provide documentation at <https://biochatter.org>, including tutorial vignettes and an API reference. All packages are developed openly and according to modern standards of software development¹⁶; we use the permissive MIT licence to encourage downstream use and development. We include a code of conduct and contributor guidelines to offer accessibility and inclusivity to all who are interested in contributing to the framework.

We provide two main applications, BioChatter Light (version 0.6.13) and BioChatter Next (version 1.3.2), which are web apps based on the Streamlit and Next.js frameworks, respectively. We also provide a REST API server implementation, BioChatter Server (version 0.5.4), which is the backend of BioChatter Next and can be used to integrate the BioChatter backend into existing frontend solutions. For more information on the packages and their use, see the [Supplementary Note: Customisation](#).

In the light of extremely rapid developments in the space of LLMs and their application, it is sensible to federate the maintenance of the many software dependencies that are regularly used in this context. This includes basic machine learning libraries, such as PyTorch¹⁷, Transformers¹⁸, LlamaCPP¹⁹, and many more; frameworks for LLM usage, such as LangChain²⁰ and Hugging Face²¹; LLM deployment frameworks, such as Xorbits Inference²² and Ollama²³; vendor-supported APIs, such as OpenAI's (for GPT, DALL-E, embeddings) and Anthropic's (for Claude); and generic open source dependencies, such as Streamlit²⁴, FastAPI²⁵, and Pydantic²⁶. Keeping these dependencies in synchronisation is a non-trivial and time-consuming task; maintaining the dependency configuration in a centralised, transparent, and version-locked manner is crucial for stability, reproducibility, and ease of use. The exact configuration for all BioChatter versions can be found in the `pyproject.toml` (<https://github.com/biocypher/biochatter/blob/main/pyproject.toml>) and `poetry.lock` (<https://github.com/biocypher/biochatter/blob/main/poetry.lock>) files of each BioChatter release.

Knowledge Graphs

Semantic grounding can facilitate the robustness and interpretability of LLM responses, which in turn can improve human-AI interaction via symbolic concepts²⁷. We leverage the strong integration between BioChatter and the BioCypher framework⁶ to seamlessly incorporate semantically enriched knowledge graph (KG) queries into the BioChatter API. During the KG creation process in BioCypher, a configuration file is employed to map KG contents to ontology terms, including detailed information about each entity. For example, we specify node properties and the source and target classes for each edge. Additionally, during the KG build, we enrich this information, saving it to a YAML file and, optionally, directly into the KG. This information is used by BioChatter to improve its understanding of the KG, enabling the LLM to query the KG more efficiently (see below). Any KG built with BioCypher is automatically compatible with BioChatter. Through this integration, we enable sophisticated knowledge management and retrieval in machine learning pipelines, in contrast to the manual and often non-reproducible methods currently used in the field.

By providing the KG context to the LLM (its specific contents and the precise spelling of all identifiers and properties), we support the LLM in generating accurate queries. The query generation process within BioChatter is methodically divided into multiple steps: identifying entities and relationships

based on the user's inquiry, estimating relevant properties for the query, and generating a syntactically correct query in the database's query language, guided by the KG schema information. Compared to the naive approach of injecting the entire schema at once, the BioChatter approach saves prompt space by separating the task into smaller steps. We first inject only the entities to select from; by leveraging information from the build process, we also remove all entities that are in the schema but not in the actual KG. In the second step, we only consider the relationships that concern the entities selected in the first step in a new conversation; i.e., we can again make use of the entire input window of the model. In the third step, we only regard the properties of entities and relationships selected in the first two steps, again in a new conversation. Finally, we use only the selected components for the final query generation prompt. This process cannot be optimised much further, given the fixed constraint of token input limits of existing LLMs. It is implemented in the `prompts.py` module. To assess the quality of this procedure, a dedicated benchmark module evaluates the query generation process using a variety of questions and KG schemata ([Supplementary Note: Benchmarking](#)).

To demonstrate this feature, we provide several vignettes, which typically include a KG build procedure and a BioChatter Light and/or BioChatter Next instance that can be executed with a single Docker Compose command. You can find these on our website (for instance, <https://biochatter.org/vignettes/kg/> and <https://biochatter.org/vignettes/custom-bclight-advanced/>) and in our supplementary notes ([Supplementary Note: Customisation](#) and [Supplementary Note: Use Case - Cancer Genetics](#)).

Retrieval-Augmented Generation

LLM confabulation (also called hallucination, their propensity to make up reasonable-sounding answers) is a significant concern in biomedical applications, where incorrect information can have severe consequences. One popular approach to mitigate this issue is through "in-context learning,"²⁸ also known as "retrieval-augmented generation" (RAG)²⁹. RAG enhances model prompts with relevant information without requiring retraining or fine-tuning, allowing any RAG prompt to be used with any LLM. While structured knowledge, such as from knowledge graphs (KGs), can be integrated, it is often more efficient to use semantic search engines to retrieve pertinent information from unstructured data sources like scientific literature, in the form of a searchable vector database³⁰.

To address the challenge of incorporating specific and relevant scientific findings into model prompts, especially when LLMs may lack access to certain research articles, BioChatter incorporates the management and integration of vector databases. This allows users to connect to a vector database, embed documents, and perform semantic searches to extract text fragments closely related to the user's query ([Supplementary Note: Retrieval-Augmented Generation](#)). The fragments retrieved as being relevant to the question can then be added to the prompt, enhancing the contextual accuracy of the model's response.

BioChatter implements these functionalities through dedicated modules: `vectorstore.py` for managing vector databases, `vectorstore_agent.py` for conducting semantic searches. An analogous implementation for KG retrieval is available in the `database_agent.py` module. Finally, the `rag_agent.py` module integrates both vector database and KG retrieval mechanisms into the BioChatter API. We demonstrate this RAG functionality via a "Retrieval-Augmented Generation" tab in our preview apps, where users can upload documents, add them to a vector database, and query the database to enrich model prompts with relevant information.

For a detailed demonstration, refer to [Supplementary Note: Retrieval-Augmented Generation](#) and visit our website (<https://biochatter.org/vignettes/rag/>).

API Calling

LLMs cannot only seamlessly interact with human users, but also with other LLMs as well as many other types of models. They understand API calls and can therefore theoretically orchestrate complex multi-step tasks^{31,32}. To allow BioChatter users to interact with external APIs, we have implemented a dedicated submodule, `api_agent`, which provides a simple interface for calling external APIs. This approach provides an abstract base class, `APIAgent`, that can be extended to implement custom API calls. It consists of the following components:

- `QueryParameters`: a Pydantic model that defines and explains the parameters required for the API call.
- `BaseQueryBuilder`: a class that uses an LLM to parameterise an API call given the query parameters and a user's question.
- `BaseFetcher`: a class that sends the API call and fetches the response.
- `BaseInterpreter`: a class that interprets the response and formats it for the user.

Child classes of those abstract components are implemented in the `api_agent` submodule to inject domain knowledge into the API calling process. For example, the OncoKB API agent (used in [Supplementary Note: Use Case - Cancer Genetics](#)) is implemented in the `oncokb.py` module and enables the LLM to correctly parameterise the OncoKB API via the knowledge encoded in the individual components. For each of the relevant APIs in biomedical research, we propose to build such a dedicated API agent and make it centrally available via the BioChatter library.

More detailed descriptions and examples can be found in our documentation (<https://biochatter.org/features/rag/#api-calling>).

Model Chaining and Reflexion

The ability of LLMs to control external software, including other LLMs, opens up a wide range of possibilities for orchestrating complex tasks. A simple example is implementing a correcting agent that receives the output of the primary model and checks it for factual accuracy; this is sometimes referred to as reflexion⁷. We implement this concept in BioChatter as a model chain, where the primary model generates a response, and the correcting agent checks it for errors. Through the modular concept, the roles of primary and correcting agents can be filled by any available model. If an error is detected, the agent can prompt the primary model to correct its output or directly forward the correction to the user. Although the correcting agent relies on its internal knowledge base, which may also be prone to errors, its independence from the primary model (due to dedicated prompts) reduces the likelihood of identical confabulations.

Initially implemented as a simple back-and-forth between two models (see the previous code at https://github.com/biocypher/biochatter/blob/v0.4.3/biochatter/llm_connect.py), this approach has been extended into more complex model chains, where the correcting agent may query external resources, such as knowledge graphs or vector databases, to ground its responses in established knowledge. These chains are relatively easy to implement, with some available out-of-the-box in frameworks such as LangGraph³³. However, as the number of links in the chain increases, so does the unpredictability of behaviour, necessitating tight control. Additionally, these chains increase the system's computational burden and time-to-answer, which is especially relevant for deployments on end-user devices.

Starting in BioChatter `v0.5.0`, we have implemented a generic approach to model chaining, using LangGraph workflows and BioChatter-specific components, such as Knowledge Graph and Vectorstore RAG (see [Supplementary Note: Retrieval-Augmented Generation](#)) and API calling (see above), to automate common workflows in biomedical applications. The abstract base class `ReflectionAgent` (in `langgraph_agent_base.py`) provides a blueprint for implementing model chains that can be adapted to arbitrary complexity. Note that we cannot attempt to fix the more general problem of LLM confabulation and thus the inherent reliability issues of these chains. What we propose is a technical framework for the application and validation of such chains in specific use cases, each of which has to be thoroughly validated by domain experts.

The approach is described in detail in our documentation (<https://biochatter.org/features/reflexion-agent/>).

Supplementary Note: The BioChatter Consortium

The BioChatter Consortium is a community of researchers and developers who are interested in the application of LLMs to biomedical research. We list here alphabetically all members of the consortium who have contributed to the development of the BioChatter framework or are building custom solutions using the framework: For comprehensiveness, we also list the projects that are currently starting or planned, but are not reported via the use cases in the appendix due to their recency. BioChatter consortium members involved as denoted below by their initials.

- Adrián G. Díaz (Interuniversity Institute of Bioinformatics in Brussels, Brussels, Belgium and Structural Biology Brussels, Vrije Universiteit Brussels, Brussels, Belgium)
- Amy Strange (Head of Software Engineering and AI, The Francis Crick Institute, London, United Kingdom)
- Andreas Maier (Institute for Computational Systems Biology, University of Hamburg, Hamburg, Germany)
- Anis Ismail (Laboratory of Multi-Omic Integrative Bioinformatics, Center for Human Genetics, Faculty of Medicine, Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, Leuven, Belgium)
- Anton Kulaga (Institute for Biostatistics and Informatics in Medicine and Ageing Research, University of Rostock, Rostock, Germany)
- Aurelien Dugourd (Heidelberg University, Faculty of Medicine and Heidelberg University Hospital, Institute for Computational Biomedicine, Heidelberg, Germany)
- Barbara Zdrzil (Chemical Biology Services, European Molecular Biology Laboratory-European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI), Wellcome Genome Campus, Hinxton, United Kingdom)
- Bastien Chassagnol (Laboratory of Probability, Statistics, and Modelling, Sorbonne University, France)
- Cankun Wang (Department of Biomedical Informatics, The Ohio State University, Columbus, Ohio, USA)
- Cyril Pommier (Université Paris-Saclay, INRAE, BioinfOmics, Plant Bioinformatics Facility, Versailles, France and Université Paris-Saclay, INRAE, URGI, Versailles, France)
- Daniele Lucarelli (Institute of Translational Cancer Research and Experimental Cancer Therapy, Technical University of Munich, Munich, Germany and Department of Computational Health, Institute of Computational Biology, Helmholtz, Munich, Germany)
- Ellen M. McDonagh (Translational Informatics Director, Open Targets, European Molecular Biology Laboratory-European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI), Wellcome Genome Campus, Hinxton, United Kingdom)
- Emma Verkinderen (Interuniversity Institute of Bioinformatics in Brussels, Université Libre de Bruxelles-Vrije Universiteit Brussel, 1050, Brussels, Belgium)
- Fernando M. Delgado-Chaves (Institute for Computational Systems Biology, University of Hamburg, Hamburg, Germany)
- Georg Fuellen (Institute for Biostatistics and Informatics in Medicine and Ageing Research (IBIMA), Rostock University Medical Center, Rostock, Germany)
- Hannah Sonntag (EMBO, Heidelberg, Germany)
- Jan Baumbach (Institute for Computational Systems Biology, University of Hamburg, Hamburg, Germany and Computational Biomedicine Lab, Department of Mathematics and Computer Science, University of Southern Denmark, Odense, Denmark)
- Jonatan Menger (Institute of Medical Biometry and Statistics, Faculty of Medicine and Medical Center – University of Freiburg, Freiburg, Germany)
- Jorge Abreu-Vicente (EMBO, Heidelberg, Germany)
- Julio Saez-Rodriguez (Heidelberg University, Faculty of Medicine and Heidelberg University Hospital, Institute for Computational Biomedicine, Heidelberg, Germany)

- Lionel Christiaen (Michael Sars Centre, University of Bergen, Bergen, Norway)
- Ludwig Geistlinger (Director of Computational Biology, Core for Computational Biomedicine, Department of Biomedical Informatics, Harvard Medical School, Boston, Massachusetts, USA)
- Luna Zacharias Zetsche (Heilbronn University of Applied Sciences, Heilbronn, Germany)
- Marlis Engelke (Heilbronn University of Applied Sciences, Heilbronn, Germany)
- Megan McNutt (Department of Biomedical Informatics, The Ohio State University, Columbus, Ohio, USA)
- Melissa Harrison (Head of Literature Services, European Molecular Biology Laboratory-European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI), Wellcome Genome Campus, Hinxton, United Kingdom)
- Melissa Hizli (GECKO Institute, Heilbronn University of Applied Sciences, Heilbronn, Germany)
- Nikolai Usanov (HEALTHy Life Extension Society (HEALES), 18 rue Jules Delhaizestraat, 1080 Brussels, Belgium)
- Nils Krehl (Heidelberg University, Faculty of Medicine and Heidelberg University Hospital, Institute for Computational Biomedicine, Heidelberg, Germany)
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- Patrick Baracho (Heilbronn University of Applied Sciences, Heilbronn, Germany)
- Qin Ma (Department of Biomedical Informatics, The Ohio State University, Columbus, Ohio, USA)
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- Sebastian Lobentanzer (Heidelberg University, Faculty of Medicine and Heidelberg University Hospital, Institute for Computational Biomedicine, Heidelberg, Germany)
- Shaohong Feng (Department of Biomedical Informatics, The Ohio State University, Columbus, Ohio, USA)
- Stefan Boeing (Bioinformatics and Biostatistics Science Technology Platform and Software Engineering and AI Science Technology Platform, The Francis Crick Institute, London, United Kingdom)
- Taru A. Muranen (Research Program in Systems Oncology, Research Programs Unit, Faculty of Medicine, University of Helsinki, Helsinki, Finland)
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- Valeriia Dragan (Institute for Computational Biomedicine, Heidelberg University, Heidelberg, Germany)
- Xiao-Ran Zhou (Institute of Bio- and Geosciences (IBG-4: Bioinformatics), Bioeconomy Science Center (BioSC), CEPLAS, Forschungszentrum Jülich, Jülich, Germany)
- Yasmin Nielsen-Tehranchian (GECKO Institute, Heilbronn University of Applied Sciences, Heilbronn, Germany)
- Yuyao Song (European Molecular Biology Laboratory-European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI), Wellcome Genome Campus, Hinxton, United Kingdom)

Support Chatbots for Bioinformatics Communities

Large bioinformatics communities have provided innumerable resources for researchers, but the volume of information, packages, and data can be overwhelming. Major platforms such as Bioconductor (<https://www.bioconductor.org>), scverse (<https://scverse.org>), and infrastructures such as ELIXIR (<https://elixir-europe.org>) provide documentation, tutorials, and help forums for users that try to navigate this complex landscape. We are working with these communities to develop, in federation, a support chatbot system that can answer user questions without the constraints of human availability, based on the specific resources and knowledge of each community. These developments are made in different contexts (ongoing project-wise collaborations, hackathons, etc.), but always in close collaboration with community members; for Bioconductor, LG is the coordinating author, for scverse, DL, and for ELIXIR, CP and SeBe.

A Conversational Platform for Drug Discovery

Open Targets (<https://www.opentargets.org>) is a public-private partnership that uses large-scale genetics and genomics to identify and prioritise potential drug targets for disease. They provide an open-source Platform (<https://platform.opentargets.org>) for the community to access their open-source data and tools. We are working with Open Targets and the Chemical and Literature services at EMBL-EBI (coordinating author: EMM, collaborating authors: BZ, MeHa) to develop a conversational platform that can answer user questions about the Open Targets Platform, data, and tools. To this end, Open Targets are funding four researchers to work on the project, starting in 2024 (project number OTAR3088).

A Conversational Platform for Experimental Design and Analysis

The Francis Crick Institute (<https://www.crick.ac.uk>) is a biomedical research institute with the mission to “understand more about how living things work to help improve treatment, diagnosis and prevention of human disease.” For this purpose, they fund numerous research groups and projects with dedicated, often disease-specific research questions. We are working with two of the Crick’s core facilities (for Bioinformatics and Biostatistics and for Software Engineering and AI) to develop a conversational platform that can help researchers design experiments, analyse data, and interpret results (coordinating authors AS and StBo). Based on the BioChatter platform and embedded into existing dashboard workflows, this platform will provide custom conversational agents for each research group and project, tailored to their specific needs, similar to the use case in [Supplementary Note: Use Case - Cancer Genetics](#).

A Platform for Publishing and Peer Review

Publishing is an essential part of the scientific process, but peer review can be slow and opaque. More and more technical considerations have to be taken into account, for instance, data / code availability, reporting, and formatting. Since the advent of preprint servers, the publication process has been accelerated, but the peer review process remains a bottleneck. Considering the great advances in natural language processing and image-to-text models, there are several opportunities to automate parts of the evaluation and quality control process of preprint publication. Applying such automations at scale will increase their value and trustworthiness, even in absence of in-depth peer review, thus promoting high quality Open Science practices. We are working with EMBO Press (coordinating author TL) and Europe PMC (EBI Literature Services, coordinating author MeHa) to develop a conversational platform that can help authors, reviewers, and editors in the publication process³⁴. First steps to the evaluation of the system have been made with the text extraction and image caption benchmarking tasks ([Supplementary Note: Benchmarking](#)). We are planning to further develop and benchmark the system to facilitate scientific communication and publication.

Supplementary Note: Retrieval-Augmented Generation

Knowledge Graph RAG

This vignette demonstrates the KG module of BioChatter as used by the BioChatter Next application. It is available online (including video and more information) at <https://biochatter.org/vignette-kg/>. We connect to a BioCypher knowledge graph (KG) to retrieve relevant information for a given question. We then use the retrieved information to generate a response to the question. The application can connect to any real-world BioCypher KG by providing the connection details in the `KG Settings` dialog.

Background

For the demonstration purposes of this vignette, we include a demo KG based on an open-source dataset of crime statistics in Manchester, because it allows us to redistribute the KG due to its small size and public domain licence, and because it is easily understood. This is the schema of the demo KG:

Pole KG schema

Usage

In BioChatter Next, we first activate the KG functionality by clicking on the `KG Settings` button in the sidebar. In the settings dialog, we can activate the KG functionality and select how many results we want to retrieve.

KG Settings

Returning to the conversation and enabling the KG functionality for the current chat (directly above the send button), we can then ask the model about the KG. The language model we use is `gpt-3.5-turbo`. The full conversation is pasted below, including the queries generated by BioChatter.

KG Conversation

In the background, the RagAgent module of BioChatter receives the question and generates a query to retrieve the desired information. This is then passed back to the primary model, which includes it in its answer generation.

Conclusion

The native integration of BioCypher KGs into the BioChatter framework allows for a seamless integration of KGs into the conversational AI. This in turn facilitates knowledge accessibility in a wide range of application domains.

Note: the apparent inability of GPT to understand certain directionalities, and how BioChatter compensates for this

Interestingly, while `gpt-3.5-turbo` mostly does a formidable job at translating natural language questions into Cypher queries, it is remarkably obtuse in certain instances. For instance, for the relationship `INVESTIGATED_BY`, which connects a `Crime` to an `Officer`, GPT consistently fails to understand that the relationship implies that the `Officer` is the one who investigates the `Crime`. Instead, it consistently interprets the relationship as if the `Crime` investigates the `Officer`: it consistently proposes the query `MATCH (o:Officer)-[:INVESTIGATED_BY]->(c:Crime) RETURN c, o` instead of the correct `MATCH (c:Crime)-[:INVESTIGATED_BY]->(o:Officer) RETURN c, o`. We were not able to change this behaviour with any contextual prompt instructions.

For this reason, the `BioChatter prompts.py` module uses the knowledge we have about the directionality of edges in the BioCypher KG to only propose options for patterns that actually exist in the KG. In the instance of `INVESTIGATED_BY`, this is the corresponding YAML definition in BioCypher:

```
investigated by:
  is_a: [fact, core]
  represented_as: edge
  label_as_edge: INVESTIGATED_BY
  input_label: INVESTIGATED_BY
  source: crime
  target: officer
```

The presence of the `source` and `target` annotations allows us to provide only the correct options to the LLM, which in turn allows the LLM to generate the correct query.

This even applies to `GPT-4` and `ChatGPT`, which we used to generate the Schema diagram above. The model immediately proposed a correct Mermaid diagram (<https://github.com/mermaid-js/mermaid>) for most of the entire schema definition YAML file, except for the relationship between `Crime` and `Officer`, which it reversed. Via the YAML we provide in the prompt, GPT has access to the correct directionality, but it still fails to understand it.

```
graph LR;
  Person(:Person) -- KNOWS --> Person
  Person -- FAMILY_REL --> Person
  Person -- LIVES_AT --> Location(:Location)
  Person -- PARTY_TO --> Crime(:Crime)
  Person -- MADE_CALL --> PhoneCall(:PhoneCall)
  Person -- RECEIVED_CALL --> PhoneCall
  Officer(:Officer) -- INVESTIGATED_BY --> Crime
  Crime -- OCCURRED_AT --> Location
  Object(:Object) -- INVOLVED_IN --> Crime

classDef node fill:#f9f,stroke:#333,stroke-width:2px;
class Person,Officer,Location,Crime,PhoneCall,Object node;
```

Here is the [full chat](#) for reference.

Conversation

The boxes below the BioChatter responses in the conversation show the queries generated by the RagAgent module.

Message From You

How many crimes happened in total?

Message From BioChatter

According to the provided statement, the total number of crimes is 28,762. This information suggests that there have been 28,762 reported crimes in the given context. However, without additional information or context, it is difficult to determine the specific time period, location, or nature of these crimes. It's important to note that crime statistics can vary depending on the source, methodology, and reporting practices. Therefore, it is always advisable to consult official crime reports or local law enforcement agencies for the most accurate and up-to-date information on crime statistics.

```
MATCH (c:Crime)
RETURN count(c) AS numberOfCrimes
```

Message From You

Where happened most crimes?

Message From BioChatter

Based on the provided statement, it appears that the location with the highest number of crimes is a parking area, with a total of 811 reported crimes. However, without additional context or information, it is difficult to determine the consistency or inconsistency of this statement with other available information. It is important to note that crime rates and locations can vary significantly depending on various factors such as the region, city, neighborhood, and specific time period being considered. To provide a more comprehensive analysis, it would be helpful to have access to a broader dataset or additional information about the specific location and its crime statistics.

```
MATCH (c:Crime)-[:OCCURRED_AT]->(l:Location)
RETURN l.address AS location, COUNT(c) AS crimeCount
ORDER BY crimeCount DESC
```

Message From You

Who were the top 3 offenders?

Message From BioChatter

Based on the provided information, the top three offenders are:

1. Phillip Williamson: According to the information given, Phillip Williamson has committed 5 crimes.
2. Jessica Kelly: The information states that Jessica Kelly has also committed 5 crimes.
3. Brian Morales: The data indicates that Brian Morales has committed 4 crimes.

These three individuals, Phillip Williamson, Jessica Kelly, and Brian Morales, are the top offenders based on the number of crimes they have committed.

```
MATCH (p:Person)-[:PARTY_TO]->(c:Crime)
RETURN p.name, p.surname, COUNT(c) AS num_crimes
ORDER BY num_crimes DESC
LIMIT 3
```

Vectorstore RAG

This vignette demonstrates the RAG module of BioChatter as used by the BioChatter Next application. This basic use case involves an LLM manuscript reading assistant and a vector database with embedded scientific manuscripts³⁵⁻³⁸. The manuscripts are recent reviews on the topic of ABC transporters (active transport proteins that often serve as efflux pumps in many tissues, with a major function of clearing exogenous substances) in drug resistance phenomena, which we currently investigate in the ovarian-cancer patient cohort in our project [DECIDER](#). Manuscripts such as these can be absent from the knowledge base of LLMs for various reasons, such as their recency or the fact that they are not open access. RAG opens up the possibility to retrieve relevant information from these manuscripts, and to inject it into the LLM's generation process.

Background

A vector database is a system that can store and retrieve vectors, which are numeric representations of multi-dimensional data³⁹. In the context of LLM technology, they are used to perform semantic search and retrieval of relevant database contents. Using a suitable embedding algorithm, i.e., a model that converts fragments of text into useful vectors of fixed length (dimensionality), the resulting embedding space of vectors can be used to determine the semantic similarity between text fragments. If the embedding algorithm is chosen correctly, fragments that are semantically similar will also be close in the vector space, allowing for efficient retrieval of relevant information.

In our case, using the added context that LLMs can provide to the embedding of sentences or paragraphs allows us to exceed the performance of traditional text similarity algorithms. For instance, the following sentences are semantically, but not lexically, similar:

- "Amyloid beta levels are associated with Alzheimer's Disease stage."
- "One of the most important clinical markers of AD progression is the amount of deposited A-beta 42."

An LLM embedding model can capture the similarity between these text fragments, even though they do not share any pertinent words. Using this mechanism allows us to retrieve relevant information given a user's question.

Usage

In BioChatter Next, we first activate the RAG functionality by clicking on the **RAG Settings** button in the sidebar. In the settings dialog, we can activate the functionality and upload an arbitrary number of documents, which is only limited by the scale of the vector database system. In this case, and for demonstration purposes, we uploaded the four manuscripts, which leads to the state shown in the screenshot below.

RAG Settings

We can now start a new conversation (using the **New Persona** button in the sidebar), for which we select the **Research manuscript helper (RAG)** persona, which includes suitable contextual prompts. Upon activating the RAG in the chat (to signal that we wish to perform RAG for our question), we can enter into a dialogue with the assistant. We use **gpt-3.5-turbo** in this example, which is a very affordable model.

RAG Conversation

Comparison with ChatGPT

We can ask ChatGPT 4 the same question (only subscription access). By employing web search, ChatGPT 4 is able to find the same study that was the RAG result we were asked about in our follow-up question (Xu et al. 2015); however, the answer is not as detailed as the answer provided by the RAG process, and includes fewer mentions of explicit studies. While it includes sensible information, there is no way of validating most of the claims made by the model. You can read the full answer [here](#). Overall, the quality of ChatGPT 4 is comparable to the RAG output, but the user has less control over the knowledge used, and the answer cannot include information that is not easily found on the web (for instance due to access restrictions). Of note, we used `gpt-3.5-turbo` in this example, which is less recent and much less expensive than GPT-4.

Asking the naive ChatGPT 3.5 (free access), the same question yields a very different answer. The free version of ChatGPT cannot search the internet, and does not provide any citations for the general answer it provides. You can read the full answer [here](#). The three full conversations are copied below.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the RAG procedure we implement is able to dramatically improve the quality of GPT-3 answers, making them comparable to GPT-4 with web search, and even surpassing it in some aspects. We invite you to try it out yourself, as we provide an instance of BioChatter Next, including GPT access and a vector database instance, free of charge at <https://next.biochatter.org>.

Conversation with BioChatter Next

Contextual Prompt

You are an assistant to a biomedical researcher.

Contextual Prompt

You have access to text fragments from one or multiple scientific manuscripts, which were retrieved by their semantic similarity to the user's question.

Contextual Prompt

Your task is to help the user understand the manuscripts and their relevance to their questions. Be concise in your explanations, provide quotes from the manuscripts where appropriate, and be open about limitations in cases where the text does not contain pertinent information.

Message From You

What is known about the CFTR protein in resistance to ovarian cancer?

Message From BioChatter

Based on the provided information, there are several studies that suggest a potential role of the CFTR (Cystic Fibrosis Transmembrane Conductance Regulator) protein in resistance to ovarian cancer. Here are some key findings from the referenced manuscripts:

1. Gene expression profiling of ovarian tumors before and after chemotherapy revealed molecular signatures of chemoresistant tumors (M, et al., 2006). This study did not specifically mention CFTR, but it provides insights into the molecular changes associated with chemoresistance.
2. ABCF2 expression, which is related to CFTR, was investigated in clear cell adenocarcinoma of the ovary. The study found a relationship between ABCF2 expression and response to chemotherapy or prognosis (Tsuda H, et al., 2010).
3. Alterations in gene copy numbers, including CFTR, were identified as a mechanism for acquired drug resistance in cancer (Yasui K, et al., 2004).

ABCF2, an Nrf2 target gene related to CFTR, was found to contribute to cisplatin resistance in 4. ovarian cancer cells (Bao L, et al., 2017).

5. CFTR was not specifically mentioned in the context of ovarian cancer, but a study on hepatocellular carcinoma found that silencing circ-TCF4.85 inhibited cancer progression through microRNA-486-5p-targeted inhibition of ABCF2 (Gao J, et al., 2020).

6. Constitutive activation of nuclear factor κ B (NF- κ B) was associated with CFTR expression and promoted cancer progression and poor prognosis in cervical cancer (Wu Z, et al., 2013).

7. High levels of CFTR expression were associated with tumor aggression in ovarian cancer, and knockdown of CFTR suppressed ovarian cancer cell proliferation (Xu J, et al., 2015).

It is important to note that while these studies suggest a potential association between CFTR and resistance to ovarian cancer, the exact mechanisms and clinical implications are still being investigated. Further research is needed to fully understand the role of CFTR in ovarian cancer resistance.

Message From You

Tell me more about the studies of aggression and knockdown of CFTR in vivo.

Message From BioChatter

Based on the provided information, there are two relevant studies regarding the aggression and knockdown of CFTR in ovarian cancer:

1. The study by Wu et al. (2013) investigated the constitutive activation of nuclear factor κ B (NF- κ B) and its contribution to CFTR expression, cancer progression, and poor prognosis in cervical cancer. Although this study is not specific to ovarian cancer, it provides insights into the role of CFTR and NF- κ B in promoting cancer progression.
2. The study by Xu et al. (2015) focused specifically on ovarian cancer and found that high levels of CFTR expression were associated with tumor aggression. They also demonstrated that knockdown of CFTR suppressed the proliferation of ovarian cancer cells in vitro and in vivo. This study suggests that CFTR may play a role in promoting ovarian cancer growth.

These studies provide evidence for the involvement of CFTR in cancer aggression and suggest that targeting CFTR could be a potential therapeutic strategy. However, it is important to note that these studies focus on different types of cancer (cervical and ovarian), and the specific mechanisms underlying CFTR's role in ovarian cancer aggression and its knockdown effects are not fully elucidated.

It is worth mentioning that the other references provided in the text fragments are not directly related to the aggression and knockdown of CFTR in ovarian cancer. They discuss topics such as the structure and function of ABC transporters, drug resistance, and inflammation in different contexts.

Conversation with ChatGPT 4

Anonymous

What is known about the CFTR protein in resistance to ovarian cancer?

ChatGPT

The CFTR protein, known as the cystic fibrosis transmembrane conductance regulator, plays a significant role in ovarian cancer. Research has shown that CFTR is expressed more in ovarian cancer tissues compared to benign ovarian tumors and normal ovaries. This overexpression of CFTR is associated with more advanced stages of ovarian cancer, poor histopathological grade, and higher serum Ca-125 levels, which are all markers of more aggressive disease. Interestingly, the serous type of ovarian cancer shows stronger CFTR staining compared to other types.

Moreover, the role of CFTR extends beyond its traditional function as an ion channel. It interacts with various intracellular signaling pathways that are crucial in cancer progression. For example, in ovarian cancer, CFTR overexpression is linked to interactions with the c-Src signaling pathway, which is involved in cellular growth.

The implications of CFTR expression in ovarian cancer are significant. In studies where CFTR was downregulated, there was a decrease in cell invasion, migration, proliferation, adhesion, and colony formation in vitro. In vivo experiments also showed that the tumorigenic abilities of ovarian cancer cells were significantly repressed when CFTR expression was reduced.

These findings highlight the complex role of CFTR in ovarian cancer and suggest that it could be a potential target for therapeutic intervention. However, it is important to note that the role of CFTR in cancer is multifaceted and varies among different types of cancers. Therefore, a detailed understanding of its function in specific cancer types, like ovarian cancer, is crucial for developing targeted treatments (<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/25738998/>, <https://jmhg.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s43042-022-00308-7>).

Conversation with ChatGPT 3.5

Anonymous

What is known about the CFTR protein in resistance to ovarian cancer?

ChatGPT

As of my last knowledge update in January 2022, there is limited direct information about the CFTR (Cystic Fibrosis Transmembrane Conductance Regulator) protein's role in resistance to ovarian cancer. CFTR is primarily associated with cystic fibrosis, a genetic disorder that affects the lungs and other organs. However, some research suggests potential links between CFTR and cancer, including ovarian cancer, although the mechanisms are not fully understood.

Here are some key points to consider:

CFTR Expression: Studies have shown that CFTR is expressed in various tissues, including the female reproductive system. Abnormal CFTR expression or function could potentially impact the development or progression of ovarian cancer. Research is ongoing to understand the role of CFTR in cancer biology.

CFTR Mutations: Certain mutations in the CFTR gene have been associated with an increased risk of cancer, although the evidence for ovarian cancer specifically is limited.

Mutations in CFTR are more commonly known for their role in cystic fibrosis. Individuals with cystic fibrosis have an increased risk of various cancers, including gastrointestinal cancers, but the link to ovarian cancer is not well-established.

Ion Transport and Cancer: CFTR is involved in ion

transport across cell membranes, and this function could potentially influence cellular processes relevant to cancer. Changes in ion transport can affect cell proliferation, apoptosis, and other cellular functions that are important in cancer development and progression. Potential Therapeutic Target: Some research suggests that modulating CFTR activity or expression could be a potential target for cancer therapy, including ovarian cancer. However, more research is needed to determine the feasibility and effectiveness of such approaches. It's important to note that the understanding of the role of CFTR in cancer, including ovarian cancer, is an evolving field, and new research findings may have emerged since my last update in January 2022. To get the most up-to-date information on this topic, I recommend consulting recent scientific literature and speaking with medical experts or researchers actively working in the field of ovarian cancer and CFTR biology.

Supplementary Note: Customisation

Applications

To demonstrate basic and advanced use cases of the framework, we provide two web apps, BioChatter Light and BioChatter Next.

BioChatter Light (<https://github.com/biocypher/biochatter-light>) is a web app based on the Streamlit framework (version 1.21.0, <https://streamlit.io>), which is written in Python and can be deployed locally or on a server. We facilitate deployment by providing a versioned Docker image (<https://hub.docker.com/r/biocypher/biochatter-light/tags>). The ease with which Streamlit allows the creation of interactive web apps in pure Python enables rapid iteration and agile development of new features, with the tradeoff of limited customisation and scalability. This framework is suitable for rapid prototyping of bespoke solutions for specific use cases. For an impression and preview of the look and feel of the platform, please visit the online preview at <https://light.biochatter.org>.

BioChatter Next (<https://github.com/biocypher/biochatter-next>) is a modern web app with server-client architecture, based on the open-source template of ChatGPT-Next-Web (<https://github.com/ChatGPTNextWeb/ChatGPT-Next-Web>). It is written combining Typescript and Python and uses Next.js (v13.4.9) for a sleek frontend and FastAPI (v0.111.0) as backend. It demonstrates the use of BioChatter in a modern web app, including full customisation and scalability. However, this comes at the cost of increased complexity and development time. We provide a versioned Docker image at <https://hub.docker.com/r/biocypher/biochatter-next/tags>. For an impression and preview of the look and feel of the platform, please visit the online preview at <https://next.biochatter.org>.

To provide seamless integration of the BioChatter backend into existing frontend solutions, we provide the server implementation at <https://github.com/biocypher/biochatter-server> and as a Docker image in our Docker Hub organisation (<https://hub.docker.com/repository/docker/biocypher/biochatter-server>).

We invite all interested researchers to select the framework that best suits their needs, or use the BioChatter server or library in their existing solutions. We gladly provide support for academic and non-commercial projects.

Simple Customisation

This vignette outlines a straightforward approach to customising the BioChatter Light Docker container for prototyping a text2cypher workflow with a focus on knowledge graph (KG) integration. We can modify the BioChatter Light Docker compose file to disable all tabs except the Knowledge Graph tab, facilitating the deployment of a streamlined KG build, deployment, and web application for LLM-based question answering. The code for this example is available at <https://github.com/biocypher/pole>.

KG Construction and Deployment

The process begins by building the KG; we use an open demo dataset for this vignette, which is based on crime statistics in Manchester. The construction, import, and deployment of the KG are handled in the first three stages of the `docker-compose.yml` file as a standard BioCypher KG build.

Customising the Docker Container

Customising BioChatter Light involves, in the simplest case, configuring environment variables within the `docker-compose.yml` file to control which components of the BioChatter Light web app are displayed. In this example, all default tabs — chatting, prompt engineering, RAG, and the correcting agent — are disabled, while the KG tab is enabled. The Docker container is then connected to the KG via the Docker network automatically.

Implementation

To implement this setup, the user clones the repository, navigates to the project directory, and initiates the Docker container (`docker compose up -d`). The configuration ensures that the KG is the sole focus of the deployed web application.

Future Expansion

The BioChatter Light platform is continually evolving, with additional tabs and customisation options expected in future updates. Users can also create their own custom tabs using the platform's modular architecture and the Streamlit framework. You can find more details in the vignette on our website: <https://biochatter.org/vignette-custom-bclight-simple/>.

Advanced Customisation

Advanced use cases involve adding your own custom components to the BioChatter Light web app. An example can be found in [Supplementary Note: Use Case - Project Management](#), including code and a live demonstration app.

We also provide customisation options for the BioChatter Next web app. Users can determine the databases to connect to, the system prompts to use, and the tools that the agent can access. In addition, new tools can be used by adding them to the BioChatter codebase, and any changes can be made to the open-source frontend to suit the project's needs. For an example, see the [Supplementary Note: Use Case - Cancer Genetics](#), including code and a live demonstration app.

Supplementary Note: Benchmarking

Background

The increasing generality of LLMs poses challenges for their comprehensive evaluation. Specifically, their ability to aid in a multitude of tasks and their great freedom in formatting the answers challenge their evaluation by traditional methods. To circumvent this issue, we focus on specific biomedical tasks and datasets with clearly defined answers. In addition, we employ automated validation of the model's responses by a second LLM for advanced assessments. For transparent and reproducible evaluation of LLMs, we implemented a benchmarking framework that allows the comparison of models, prompt sets, and all other components of the pipeline.

Since the biomedical domain has its own tasks and requirements⁴⁰, we created a bespoke benchmark that allows us to be more precise in the evaluation of components. This is complementary to the existing, general-purpose benchmarks and leaderboards for LLMs⁴¹⁻⁴³. Furthermore, to prevent leakage of the benchmark data into the training data of the models^{8,44}, we implemented an encrypted pipeline that contains the benchmark datasets and is only accessible to the workflow that executes the benchmark.

Implementation

The BioChatter living benchmarking framework examines a matrix of component combinations using the parameterisation feature of Pytest⁴⁵. The Pytest framework is implemented at <https://github.com/biocypher/biochatter/blob/main/benchmark>, and more information is available at <https://biochatter.org/features/benchmark/>. Implementation details and the exact tasks and questions we use can be found there. This implementation allows for the automated evaluation of all possible combinations of components, such as LLMs, prompts, and datasets. At the time of writing, the number of individual test results in the benchmark is 65 492 (including replicates).

For most open-source models, the library of built-in models from Xorbits Inference (v0.14.1) provided ready-to-use models⁴⁶. We performed the benchmarks on a MacBook Pro with an M3 Max chip with 40-core GPU and 128GB of RAM. As a default, we ran each test five times to account for the stochastic nature of LLMs. We generally set the temperature to the lowest value possible for each model to decrease fluctuation.

The Pytest matrix uses a hash-based system to evaluate whether a model-dataset combination has been run before. Briefly, the hash is calculated from the dictionary representation of the test parameters, and the test is skipped if the combination of hash and model name is already present in the database. This hashing optimises for efficiency by only running modified or newly added tests. The individual dimensions of the matrix are:

- **LLMs:** Testing proprietary (OpenAI) and open-source models (commonly using the Xorbits Inference API and HuggingFace models) against the same set of tasks is the primary aim of our benchmarking framework. We facilitate the automation of testing by including a programmatic way of deploying open-source models.
- **prompts:** Since model performance can dramatically rely on the used prompts, a set of prompts for each task with varying degrees of specificity and fixed as well as variable components is used to evaluate this variability.

- **datasets:** We test various tasks using a set of datasets for each task in question-answer-style.
- **model quantisations:** We test a set of quantisations for each model (where available) to account for the trade-off between model size, inference speed, and performance.
- **stochasticity:** To account for variability in model responses, we include a parameter to run each test multiple times and generate summary statistics.

The benchmark is updated upon the release of new models and extensions to the datasets, and continuously available at <https://biochatter.org/benchmark>. We will run the benchmark on new models and variants (including fine-tuned models) upon requests from the community, which can be made on GitHub using our issue template (<https://github.com/biocypher/biochatter/issues/new/choose>). The living benchmark process is inspired by test-driven development, meaning test cases are created based on specific features or behaviours that are desired. When a model doesn't initially produce the optimal response, which is often the case, adjustments are made to various elements of the framework, including prompts or functions, to enhance the model's effectiveness. Monitoring the model's performance on these tests over time allows us to assess the framework's reliability and pinpoint areas that need improvement.

To prevent leakage of benchmarking data (and subsequent contamination of future LLMs), we implemented an encryption routine on the benchmark datasets. The encryption is performed using a hybrid encryption scheme, where the data are encrypted with a symmetric key, which is in turn encrypted with an asymmetric key. The datasets are stored in a dedicated encrypted pipeline that is only accessible to the workflow that executes the benchmark. These processes are implemented at <https://github.com/biocypher/llm-test-dataset> (private repository) and accessed from the benchmark procedure in BioChatter.

Results

We will illustrate the process of benchmarking by giving an example of the knowledge graph query generation task, and then move on to the general benchmark results.

Example: BioChatter-BioCypher Cross-Functionality

A key feature of BioChatter is its native integration with BioCypher knowledge graphs (KGs). Via the schema configuration of BioCypher KGs, BioChatter can better transmit the context and syntactic requirements of any given KG to the LLM. A central aspect of our benchmark is that each feature should have corresponding tests in the benchmark to assess the models' performance on that feature. We implemented a battery of tests that evaluate the performance of LLMs with and without the use of BioChatter's prompt engine on the task of text2cypher query generation.

For this purpose, we created KG schema definitions specific for the benchmark; for instance, a schema for a biomedical KG. Given this schema and some instructions, the models are tasked with generating a Cypher query that can answer the user's question. In this case, they do it either via BioChatter's prompt engine, or by using the schema definition that BioChatter uses in the prompt engine; that is, both models have access to the same information. The main difference is that the prompt engine decomposes the task into multiple steps (entity selection, relationship selection, etc.), while the model without prompt engine has to generate the query in one step.

Here is an example of a test case, defined in our test data YAML file:

```

biocypher_query_generation:
  - case: simple
    input:
      kg_schema: gene_kg
      prompt: What is the name of the disease with ICD10 code 'E10'?
    expected:
      entities: ["Disease"]
      relationships: []
      relationship_labels: {}
      properties:
        Disease: ["name", "ICD10"]
      parts_of_query:
        [
          "^MATCH",
          "RETURN",
          "([a-zA-Z]*:Disease)",
          "WHERE [a-zA-Z]*\\.ICD10|{ICD10:",
        ]

```

[...]

```

kg_schemas:
  gene_kg:
    [...]
  disease:
    represented_as: node
    input_label: Disease
    is_relationship: false
    preferred_id: doid
    present_in_knowledge_graph: true
    properties:
      DSM5: str
      ICD10: str
      name: str
    [...]

```

In this test case, the model is asked to generate a Cypher query that retrieves the name of a disease with a specific ICD10 code, from a knowledge graph that contains entities of type "Disease" with properties "name" and "ICD10". The test case has a name (`simple`) for later analysis, and two inputs: the schema of the knowledge graph (`gene_kg`) and the prompt (`What is the name of the disease with ICD10 code 'E10'?`). The definition of the disease entity type is provided in the `kg_schemas` section, with all other entities and relationships defined in the same way. The expected output of the model is defined in the `expected` section, with the entities, relationships, and properties that the model should use in the query, as well as the parts of the query that the model should generate.

In this test case, we use regular expressions to match the generated query against the expected parts of the query, allowing for some flexibility in the model's response. This allows models to receive a non-zero score even if the query would not return a result, as long as some parts of the query are correct, such as formatting. For instance, we typically want the query to start with a `MATCH` clause (no additional text before it), and to end on a `RETURN` statement. Determining the correct parts of the query that the model should generate requires knowledge of Cypher query language by the person designing the test case. The score (accuracy) of the model is then the number of correct parts of the query that the model generates, divided by the total number of parts of the query that the model should generate.

In general, some LLMs perform fairly well on text2cypher tasks, while others make errors in formatting or ignore the instruction to only provide the query, but no additional text (Figure 3). Query generation, given correctly preselected entities, properties, and relationships, seems to be a task that most models can handle. Entity selection and selecting properties that exist seem to be the easiest tasks, while selecting relationships and the correct properties yield mixed results. The integrated task of generating the query de novo, including the selection of entities, relationships, and properties, is the most difficult task for all models (yet in some cases is handled well by OpenAI's top models).

Figure 3: Benchmark results: text2cypher query generation. Performance of different LLMs on the BioChatter benchmark datasets for text2cypher query generation tasks; the y-axis value indicates the average performance across all tasks for each model. Center line, median; box limits, upper and lower quartiles; whiskers, 1.5x interquartile range; points, outliers.

Across all tested models, the use of BioChatter's prompt engine significantly improves the performance of the models in generating correct queries compared to the naive approach of instructing the model with the full schema information (0.444 ± 0.11 vs. 0.818 ± 0.11 , unpaired t-test $P < 0.001$, Figure 4). See an example of a prompt in the [Model prompts] section below. All granular and updated results for query generation tasks are available at <https://biochatter.org/benchmark/results/#biocypher-query-generation>.

Figure 4: Benchmark results: text2cypher query generation with and without prompt engine. Performance of different LLMs on the BioChatter benchmark datasets for text2cypher query generation tasks, with and without the use of BioChatter's prompt engine; the y-axis value indicates the average performance across all tasks for each model. Center line, median; box limits, upper and lower quartiles; whiskers, 1.5x interquartile range; points, outliers.

The KG query generation was prompted as follows (system prompt):

You are a database expert. Please write a Cypher query to retrieve information for the user. The schema of the graph is defined as follows:

```
{"disease":  
  {"represented_as": "node",  
   "input_label": "Disease",  
   "is_relationship": false,  
   "preferred_id": "doid",  
   "present_in_knowledge_graph": true,  
   "properties":  
     {"DSM5": "str",  
      "ICD10": "str",  
      "name": "str"}  
  },  
  [...] # full schema definition  
}
```

Only return the query, nothing else.

This was followed by the user's question for all benchmark cases. The detailed cases and prompts are available open source at <https://github.com/biocypher/biochatter/blob/main/benchmark>.

General

Analysis of these benchmarks confirmed the prevailing opinion of OpenAI's leading role in LLM performance (Figure 5). Since the benchmark datasets were created to specifically cover functions relevant in BioChatter's application domain, the benchmark results are primarily a measure of the LLMs' usefulness in our applications.

OpenAI's GPT models (gpt-4 and gpt-3.5-turbo) lead by some margin on overall performance and consistency, but several open-source models reach high performance in specific tasks. Of note, while the newer version (0125) of gpt-3.5-turbo outperforms (overall median accuracy 0.87) its previous version (0613, median accuracy 0.76) and even gpt-4-0613 (median accuracy 0.78) and the newest gpt-4-turbo-2024-04-09 (median accuracy 0.83), version 0125 of gpt-4 shows a significant drop in performance (median accuracy 0.73). The most recent gpt-4o-2024-05-13 (0.73) and gpt-4o-mini-2024-07-18 (0.7) models show even lower performance.

While a thorough analysis of the reasons for these differences is beyond the scope of this work, it is likely that the models' post-training instructions play a significant role. There have been multiple reports of OpenAI's models becoming "lazier" over time, and the system prompt that is used to align OpenAI's models has reached unprecedented length and complexity, nearing 2000 tokens. These factors cannot be scientifically studied as they are based on reports from the community; OpenAI's models are closed-source and their configuration and post-training adjustments have not been disclosed.

Anthropic's Claude-3-Opus (0.77) and Claude-3.5-Sonnet (0.76) models perform comparably to the 0613 versions of gpt-3.5 and gpt-4, but do not reach the performance of top OpenAI models.

The performance of open-source models appears to depend on their quantisation level, i.e., the bit-precision used to represent the model's parameters. For models that offer quantisation options, performance apparently plateaus or even decreases after the 4- or 5-bit mark (Figure 5). A notable exception is the llama-3.1-instruct model, which performs similarly well across all quantisation levels, and even between its 70B and 8B parameter versions, which may indicate a ceiling effect with respect to our benchmark tasks. Overall, there is no apparent correlation between model size and performance (Pearson's $r = 0.171$, $p < 0.001$). The openhermes-2.5 model (7 billion parameters, 5-bit) also performs well in our benchmark, on par with llama-3.1-instruct. It is based on Mistral 7B and was fine-tuned on GPT-4 generated data, which makes it a complicated hybrid model⁴⁷.

Figure 5: Benchmark results: general. Performance of different LLMs (indicated by colour) on the BioChatter benchmark datasets; the y-axis value indicates the average (median) performance across all tasks for each model/size. X-axis jittered for better visibility. While the closed-source models from OpenAI mostly show highest performance, open-source models can perform comparably, but show high variance. Measured performance does not seem to correlate linearly with size (indicated by point size) and quantisation (bit-precision) of the models. *: Of note, many characteristics of OpenAI/Anthropic models are not public, and thus their bit-precision (as well as the exact size of gpt-4 and claude) is subject to speculation.

Information Extraction from Text

We also evaluated the performance of LLMs on the classical natural language processing task of named entity recognition (NER). We used the recently generated SourceData dataset⁴⁸ for this task, which focuses on figure captions of scientific articles. We tested the models' ability to extract assay information, chemical entities, context, diseases, entities, experiment information, hypotheses, interventions, gene identifiers, and statistical information, including significance, from the figure captions. The tested tasks in combination with models, quantisation, and prompts resulted in a total of 4653 test cases at the time of writing.

The performance of models was mixed, but generally showed a high variance across tasks, which is likely due to their varying complexity (Figure 6). While it seems easy for some models (GPT, openhermes) to distinguish whether a figure caption contains an experiment or not, other tasks, such as extracting chemical or gene entities, are difficult for all models. The most difficult task seems to be

the extraction of an underlying hypothesis from a figure caption, which no model was able to solve; this is in line with expectations. The granular and updated results are available at <https://biochatter.org/benchmark/results/#text-extraction>.

Figure 6: Benchmark results: text extraction. Performance of different LLMs on the SourceData dataset for text extraction tasks; the y-axis value indicates the performance for each model (indicated by colour). X-axis jittered for better visibility. While some tasks appear easy for some models, others are difficult across the board.

Text-to-image Recognition

In the context of SourceData⁴⁸, we also evaluated the performance of LLMs on the task of text-to-image recognition. As an initial experiment, we assessed the models' ability to tell whether a given figure caption belongs to a figure or not. For this purpose, we created pairs of figure captions and image panels from the SourceData dataset in two ways: one where the figure caption belongs to the image panel, and one where it does not (we sample it randomly from all captions). Selecting 20 figures and captions at random, five times, across the entire dataset (2770 panels and captions at the time of writing), we asked current text-to-image models to predict whether the caption belongs to the image. An example can be seen in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Example figure caption and image panel. Example of a figure caption and image panel from the SourceData dataset⁴⁸. The caption reads: "Microinjection of GABA (5 mM for 100 ms, sr/slm border in the presence of CGP55845/TTX, arrowheads) induced a pronounced depolarization in WT neurons (black) that was abolished in the absence of CO₂/HCO₃⁻ (grey)."

The current models with image capability from OpenAI all show excellent performance on this task, with balanced accuracy scores of 96% (gpt-4o-2024-05-13), 98% (gpt-4o-mini-2024-07-18), and 99% (gpt-4-turbo-2024-05-13). Of note, we also asked the models to give the confidence of their prediction, which does not appear to be correlated with the correctness of the prediction (Figure 8). Regardless of correctness, the models appear to answer with either high (8, 9, 10) or low (1, 2, 3) confidence in a bimodal distribution. Of note, model performance was so good that we did not have many incorrect predictions to analyse.

Figure 8: Benchmark results: text-to-image recognition confidence. Self-reported confidence of different LLMs on the prediction task of a caption belonging to a figure panel.

We will expand this analysis, including the use of open source models, and add other knowledge extraction tasks in future benchmarks, which we will implement in the planned BioGather framework for knowledge extraction. The results will be updated and made available at <https://biochatter.org/benchmark/results/#image-caption-yesno>.

Medical Question Answering

We evaluated the performance of LLMs on the task of medical question answering using a bespoke dataset created by medical and medical informatics students from Heidelberg and Heilbronn, Germany (consortium authors LZZ, ME, MeHi, PB, YNT). The dataset is based on medical exams of doctors in Germany and contains questions in single-choice, multiple-choice, and free-text formats. The exact categories of answers were 'dichotomous', 'multiple_choice', 'single_choice', 'one_word', and 'regex'. The domains of knowledge tested were 'biochemistry', 'cardiology', 'dermatology', 'eeg_data', 'emergency', 'medication', 'mental_disorders', 'oncology', 'physiology', 'math', and 'anatomy'. In combination with the various models, quantisations, and prompts, this resulted in a total of 10 495 test cases at the time of writing.

Overall, OpenAI's `gpt-4o-mini-2024-07-18` and `gpt-4-turbo-2024-04-09` models performed best on this task (both with an accuracy of 0.84), but were closely followed by `llama-3.1-instruct:70:ggufv2:IQ4_XS` (70B parameters, 4-bit quantised, accuracy 0.82) and `claude-3-opus-20240229` (0.81). Other llama-3.1-instruct models (including the ones with 8B parameters), OpenAI gpt-4 models, and Anthropic models (Claude 3.5 Sonnet) gave results between 0.73 and 0.8 accuracy. OpenAI's gpt-3.5-turbo achieved slightly lower (0.67) accuracy, in line with expectations and previous reports. Following were llama-3-instruct models (4-, 5-, 6-, and 8-bit) with

accuracies between 0.62 and 0.64; openhermes-2.5 models came next with accuracies between 0.54 and 0.59. The full and continuously updated table of results is available at <https://biochatter.org/benchmark/results/#medical-exam-question-answering>.

The questions were partially translated into English to allow for a broader evaluation of the models and effects of language. However, we did not find a significant difference in performance between the German and English questions, overall (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Benchmark results: language differences. Performance of different LLMs on the medical question answering dataset for German (de) and English (en) questions. Center line, median; box limits, upper and lower quartiles; whiskers, 1.5x interquartile range; points, outliers.

Language differences per domain were also not significant overall, except for slight trends, which in most cases favoured the English language (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Benchmark results: language differences per domain. Performance of different LLMs on the medical question answering dataset for German and English questions, split by domain. Center line, median; box limits, upper and lower quartiles; whiskers, 1.5x interquartile range; points, outliers.

The performance of models varied widely across domains and tasks, with EEG data and oncology questions being the easiest to answer, and maths being the most difficult, in line with general expectations (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Benchmark results: medical question answering by domain. Performance of different LLMs on the medical question answering dataset for different medical domains. Center line, median; box limits, upper and lower quartiles; whiskers, 1.5x interquartile range; points, outliers.

In regard to the tasks, the models performed best in scenarios where their answer was checked using regular expressions ('regex'), with dichotomous questions (mainly yes/no questions) being the second easiest to answer. Answering with single words ('one_word') and answering standard format questions ('single-choice', 'multiple-choice') was much more difficult for the models (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Benchmark results: medical question answering by task. Performance of different LLMs on the medical question answering dataset for different question types. Center line, median; box limits, upper and lower quartiles; whiskers, 1.5x interquartile range; points, outliers.

Supplementary Note: Use Case - Cancer Genetics

This supplementary note is available in our documentation web page with additional details (<https://biochatter.org/vignettes/custom-decider-use-case>).

Background

Personalised medicine allows us to address the individual genetic makeup of patients. In the context of cancer, this facilitates the stratification and subsequent assignment of patients to treatment arms of clinical trials. However, the complexity that arises from the multitude of genetic alterations, the interplay of genetic and environmental factors, the heterogeneity of tumours and patient histories, and the large amount of data generated from different high-throughput technologies poses a challenge to data interpretation and decision-making¹.

We are working on a support system for clinical geneticists and doctors to facilitate these tasks in the DECIDER consortium (<https://deciderproject.eu>). The following use case is closely aligned to the current workflow and vision of our consortium. You can find the open source code, as well as a live demonstration of the application, at <https://github.com/biocypher/decider-genetics>.

In this use case, we demonstrate how BioChatter can be used to develop an integrated workflow for a cancer geneticist to facilitate interpretation of genetic data of ovarian cancer patients in order to inform the tumour board about feasible treatment options. The input data include patient-level catalogues of genomic aberrations processed from whole genome sequencing data, the patients' clinical history, data from open resources, and relevant publications from the biomedical literature. For identifiable data, we here use synthetic data to allow sharing.

Sources of knowledge

We integrate knowledge from diverse resources, using a BioCypher workflow to build a knowledge graph of:

1. Processed whole genome sequencing data of ovarian cancer patients (synthetic data)
 - genomic changes
 - classified by consequence (protein truncation, amino acid change)
 - algorithmic prediction of deleteriousness
 - variant identifiers
 - allele dosages
 - gene allele copy number (amplifications, deletions, loss-of-heterogeneity)
 - mutation pervasiveness (estimate of number of affected alleles, or suspected subclonality)
 - proportion of cancer cells in the sample (tumour purity)

the patients' clinical history (synthetic data)

2.
 - personal information (age at diagnosis, BMI, etc.)
 - treatment history, known side effects, clinical response
 - lab test results (blood, imaging, histopathology)
 - common treatment-relevant mutations (BRCA), HR deficiency, PARP-inhibitor maintenance
3. data from open resources (real data)
 - variant annotations (as provided by the genetics pipeline of the DECIDER consortium)
 - gene annotations (as provided by the genetics pipeline of the DECIDER consortium)
 - pathway / process annotations (from public databases such as Gene Ontology⁴⁹)
 - drug annotations (from OncoKB⁹)

In addition, we provide access to more resources via the RAG and API agents:

1. relevant publications from PubMed (real data) embedded in a vector database (<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/?term=high%20grade%20serous%20ovarian%20cancer&filter=simsearch2.ffrft&filter=pubt.review&filter=pubt.systematicreview>)
2. relevant knowledge streamed live from OncoKB (see below) via API access through BioChatter's API agent

The geneticist's workflow

Personalized cancer therapy is typically guided by identifying somatic genomic driver events in specific genes. For hotspot mutations with experimentally validated effects, the therapeutic approach is clear. However, the same genes and pathways can also be affected by rare somatic events, whose impact and clinical relevance are more difficult to determine. This creates an area of uncertainty ("grey zone") where expert genetic analysis is needed to evaluate the genomic data of the specific cancer and external evidence.

A comprehensive backend processing of whole-genome sequencing data generates a catalog of somatic changes, annotated for their consequences and the expected number of affected gene copies. With proper identifiers, this catalog can be linked to external resources, enabling appropriate clinical interpretation. For example, protein-truncating or pathogenic missense mutations in BRCA1 gene, when combined with a loss of the intact allele in cancer, confer sensitivity to PARP-inhibitor treatment. On the other hand, a heterozygous pathogenic missense mutation or amplification of the ERBB2 gene would suggest sensitivity to trastuzumab.

Fully exploiting the actionable grey zone requires flexible integration of patient data with literature on drug targets, mechanisms of action, and resistance phenomena. The standard resource for this information is OncoKB⁹, which we make available via two avenues: drug annotations on actionability are collected from <https://www.oncokb.org/actionable-genes#sections=Tx> and added to the KG (since

they are not available via the OncoKB API), and all API-available information from OncoKB can be called via the BioChatter API agent.

In addition to data evaluation, the geneticist must also compare against knowledge from the vast biomedical literature. To facilitate access to pertinent information, we use semantic search on a corpus of relevant publications, in this case from <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/?term=high%20grade%20serous%20ovarian%20cancer&filter=simsearch2.ffrft&filter=pubt.review&filter=pubt.systematicreview>. This allows quick fact-checks of the geneticist's findings, for instance with respect to established treatments or resistance mechanisms.

In summary, the main contributions of our use case to the productivity of this workflow are:

- making processed and analysed genomic data locally available in a centralised resource by building a custom KG
- allowing comparison to literature via semantic search inside a vector database with relevant publications
- providing live access to external resources via the API agent

We streamline and strengthen the workflow by incorporating calculations and data aggregations, which are typically error-prone if done manually, into the KG build process. In addition, we allow the use of a complex public API via natural language. Prospectively, there are many more subtle questions to be answered in a cancer geneticist's workflow, which we will continue developing with our ongoing consortia, such as DECIDER, Open Targets, and the ELIXIR community. We aim to exploit synergies between the resources we maintain, for instance by collecting drug sensitivity data from Open Targets to be used in the context of molecular tumour board decisions.

Building the application

We will explain how to use the BioCypher ecosystem, specifically, BioCypher and BioChatter, to build a decision support application for a cancer geneticist. The code base for this use case, including all details on how to set up the KG and the application, is available at <https://github.com/biocypher/decider-genetics>. You can find live demonstrations of the applications at links provided in the README of the repository. The build procedures can be reproduced by cloning the repository and running `docker-compose up -d` (or the equivalent for the Next app) in the root directory (note that the default configuration requires authentication with OpenAI services). The process involves the following steps:

1. Identifying data sources and creating a knowledge graph schema
2. Building the KG with BioCypher from the identified sources
3. Using BioChatter Light to develop and troubleshoot the KG application
4. Customising BioChatter Next to yield an integrated conversational interface
5. Deploying the applications

Identifying data sources and creating a knowledge graph schema

We examine the data sources described above and design a KG schema that can accommodate the data. The configuration file, `schema_config.yaml`, can be seen in the `config` directory of the repository. The schema should also be designed with LLM access in mind; performance in generating specific queries can be adjusted for in step three (troubleshooting using BioChatter Light). We created a bespoke adapters for the genetics data of the DECIDER cohort according to the output format of the genetics pipeline, and reused existing adapters for the open resources. They can be found in the `decider_genetics/adapters` directory of the repository. For this use case, we created synthetic data to stand in for the real data for privacy reasons; the synthetic data are available in the `data` directory.

Building the KG with BioCypher

In the dedicated adapters for the DECIDER genetics data, we pull the data from the synthetic data files and build the KG. We perform simplifying computations, as described above, to facilitate standard workflows (such as counting alleles, identifying pathogenic variants, and calculating tumour purity). We mold the data into the specified schema in a transparent and reproducible manner by configuring the adapters (see the `decider_genetics/adapters` directory).

After creating the schema and adapters, we run the build script to populate the KG. BioCypher is configured using the `biocypher_config.yaml` file in the `config` directory. Using the Docker Compose workflow included in the BioCypher template repository, we build a containerised version of the KG. We can inspect the KG in the Neo4j browser at `http://localhost:7474` after running the build script. Any changes, if needed, can be made to the configuration of schema and adapters.

Using BioChatter Light to develop and troubleshoot the KG application

Upon deploying the KG via Docker, we can use a custom BioChatter Light application to interact with the KG. Briefly, we remove all components except the KG interaction panel via environment variables in the `docker-compose.yaml` file (see also [Supplementary Note: Customisation](#)). This allows us to start the KG and interact with it using an LLM in a reproducible manner with just one command. We can then test the LLM-KG interaction by asking questions and examining the generated queries and its results from the KG. Once we are satisfied with the KG schema and LLM performance, we can advance to the next step.

Customising BioChatter Next to yield an integrated conversational interface

We can further customise the Docker workflow to start the BioChatter Next application, including its REST API middleware `biochatter-server`. In addition to deploying all software components, we can also customise its appearance and functionality. Using the `biochatter-next.yaml` configuration file (in `config`, as all other configuration files), we can adjust the welcome message, how-to-use section, the system prompts for the LLM, which tools can be used by the LLM agent, the connection details of externally hosted KG or vectorstore, and other parameters. We then start BioChatter Next using a dedicated Docker Compose file, which includes the `biochatter-server` middleware and the BioChatter Next application.

Deploying the applications

The final step is to deploy one or both applications on a server. Using the Docker Compose workflow, we can deploy the applications in many different environments, from local servers to cloud-based solutions. The environment supplied by the Docker software allows for high reproducibility and easy scaling. The BioChatter Light app can be used for testing, but also to provide a simple one-way interface to the KG for users who do not need the full conversational interface. The BioChatter Next app can be configured to connect to KG and vectorstore deployments on different servers, allowing for a distributed architecture and dedicated maintenance of components; but it can also be deployed in tandem from one Docker Compose, for smaller setups or local use. Visit the website for more information and demonstrations of the applications (<https://biochatter.org/vignettes/custom-decider-use-case>).

Supplementary Note: Use Case - Project Management

This supplementary note is available in our documentation web page with additional details (<https://biochatter.org/vignettes/custom-bclight-advanced>).

Background

Managing a scientific group with multiple interdependent projects is challenging. A tool to aid in project management can enhance productivity and communication, freeing up scientists' "thinking time."⁵⁰ Essential components for this are effective data management and simple interfaces, which we can achieve via a custom BioCypher and BioChatter implementation.

A GitHub Project board serves as the data source for this tool, connecting to code repositories, issues, and pull requests. You can find a more detailed description of this use case, as well as a web link to the project board and live demonstration application, in the corresponding vignette on the BioChatter documentation page (<https://biochatter.org/vignettes/custom-bclight-advanced>) and the corresponding GitHub repository (<https://github.com/biocypher/project-planning>).

Building the Knowledge Graph (KG)

A BioCypher adapter for the GitHub GraphQL API pulls data from the GitHub Project board to build the KG. Based on the adaptation of a previously existing adapter, this step required minimal time investment (approximately 3 hours), which is a key principle of BioCypher. The KG schema includes various fields such as Leads, Projects, Comments, and more, adaptable through BioCypher mechanisms. Once created, the BioCypher adapter can be used on any GitHub project board with minimal modifications. A GitHub token is required to run the script.

The adapter

The fields we retrieve from the GitHub API are:

- **Title** : the title of the project item
- **Assignees** : the team members assigned to the project item
- **Status** : the status of the project item (e.g., **To Do** , **In Progress** , **Done**)
- **Labels** : the custom labels assigned to the project item (e.g., **Help Wanted** , **To Discuss**)
- **Linked pull requests** : the pull requests linked to the project item
- **Milestone** : the milestone associated with the project item
- **Repository** : the repository where the project item is located
- **Reviewers** : the team members assigned to review the project item
- **Priority** : the priority of the project item (e.g., **P0** , **P1** , **P2**)

- **Size** : the size of the project item (e.g., S, M, L)
- **Estimate** : the estimated time to complete the project item
- **Iteration** : the iteration in which the project item is scheduled
- **Start date** : the start date of the project item
- **End date** : the end date of the project item

For each item on the project board, we retrieve a unique combination of these fields, as well as the body text and comments associated with the project item. These are ingested into the knowledge graph via BioCypher, to be later used for retrieval by the LLM.

The adapter also provides `mutate` functions that can create, modify, move, or delete projects on the board. While these functions could be parameterised by the LLM in response to a user request, we have not implemented this functionality in the current demonstration application.

Adding Tabs to BioChatter Light

BioChatter Light's modular architecture allows for flexible layout changes. For this project, three new tabs were added: `Last Week's Summary`, `This Week's Tasks`, and `Task Settings`. These tabs provide an overview of completed tasks, upcoming tasks for the group and team members, and configuration settings for queries and LLM instructions.

The tabs were implemented with around 100 lines of code each using the Streamlit framework and added to the BioChatter Light codebase (<https://github.com/biocypher/biochatter-light/blob/main/components/panels/project.py>). Environment variables can be configured to enable or disable specific tabs.

Configuring the BioChatter Light Docker Container

The Docker container for BioChatter Light was configured to display only the new tabs, with environment variables setting the page title, header, and subheader. The `docker-compose.yml` file in the repository outlines the full configuration. Deployment on a cloud VM involves cloning the repository and running Docker commands, ensuring `OPENAI_API_KEY` and `BIOCYPHER_GITHUB_PROJECT_TOKEN` are provided.

Deployment Tips

For deployment, using a reverse proxy with Nginx is recommended for HTTPS and domain name provision. An example Nginx configuration is provided in our documentation. We also advise setting up certification with Let's Encrypt using Certbot. We also provide options to ensure that the Neo4j deployment of the database is accessible and secure, with options for network-only access or a secure connection.

Conclusion

This vignette demonstrates the creation of a custom BioChatter Light web app for project management, highlighting the flexibility and ease of use of the framework. The project management

tool serves as a proof of concept, aiming to evolve into a conversational assistant that supports administrative tasks for larger groups and organisations. The capabilities of GitHub Projects and their API facilitate multi-level project management, allowing task management for smaller teams, larger groups, and whole organisations.

Tying the connection to biomedical research, the tool can be adapted to include capabilities outside of project management, connecting to other BioChatter capabilities, such as literature search, knowledge graph RAG, and API calling. This will enable an Integrated Research Environment (IRE, similar to Integrated Development Environments, IDEs, in programming), with LLMs acting as support agents for researchers that manage daily processes, data access, communication, and the use of bioinformatics tools.